

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOLOGY IN DENTAL PRACTICE**Yarmuhammedov Nabijon Navruzovich****Kosimova Dilafruz****Samarkand State Medical University**

Annotation: This article is devoted to the problem of psychological stability of patients during dental treatment. Great attention is paid to different types of individuals and their attitude towards medical practice. The article also provides statistics on the impact of negative dental treatment experiences on patients in the past and their relationship to the present.

Keywords: dental, obsessive, medical, psychological type.

Introduction : Despite the modern treatment of dental diseases, the high qualifications and professionalism of dentists, modern equipment allows painless dental interventions, dentists are often faced with symptoms of situational anxiety and fear of patients. Statistics show that 55-83% of patients experience anxiety and excitement before a dental appointment, and about 5% of respondents experience the strongest fear when contacting this specialist [1. Page 31]. Such a high rate is associated with unsuccessful experiences in childhood and adolescence, lack of confidence in the doctor's qualifications or large financial losses during hospitalization and treatment, and it is noteworthy that most patients experience fear with the integration of mental disorders. Modern standards purchased incompatible conditions during treatment. The modern approach in the treatment of dental patients is to carry out minimally invasive treatments with quick recovery. It should be added that excessive excitement during hospitalization can be caused by somatic diseases or serious emergency conditions . Different types of patients may react differently to the upcoming dental procedure. People with psychopathic and ignorant personality types are characterized by a rejection of the disease. Such

patients often do not perform preventive examinations and do not neglect oral health. They seek help in "extreme cases", mainly diseases that cause discomfort or severe pain (myelitis, acute periodontitis) . Anxious individuals of dental patients require more attention from doctors and other medical personnel. Complaints about hypertrophy and hypertrophy are characteristic of such patients. Even without the most serious diagnosis, fears for life and health can arise. When treating such patients, it is recommended to choose an integrated method that includes a detailed description of the patient's condition. It is necessary to provide the most comprehensive course of treatment, monitor it, constantly stimulate it and thereby determine it in order to achieve a positive treatment result. The communicative-interpretive model is suitable for uneducated people, while the counseling model is suitable for educated people who delve into the essence of the problem. Dentists must have the ability to communicate professionally with patients, ethics and dental science.

To conclude: Therefore, in any case, communication should begin in the same way, but at the appointment, the doctor must change his negotiation tactics if necessary .

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